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Why does hatred persist in X? Insights from the Spanish media

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Declaration of conflicting interest

Authors declare no conflict of interest

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Ethical approval and informed consent statements

The presented study analyzes publicly available data collected from the X platform, which is anonymized and analyzed in aggregate form. Therefore, it did not require ethical approval.

Data availability

The final database of the analyzed data can be accessed through the URL: <https://acortar.link/Ofx0Mi>

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Abstract

This study examines hate speech persistence on X (formerly Twitter) in Spanish digital media, using an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design. The research analyzed 9,894 hate messages from 2.1 million comments from five Spanish digital news outlets (20 Minutos, ABC, La Vanguardia, El Mundo, and El País) collected between January 2021 and May 2022, with verification in 2024. The study used machine learning algorithms, ANOVA, and Random Forest modeling to investigate the factors influencing message persistence versus deletion. The findings show that 88% of hate speech messages remained active after three years, challenging the traditional "pyramid of hate" models. Message intensity showed no statistical significance ($p = 0.512$) in predicting removal, whereas categorical factors emerged as the primary determinants. Random Forest analysis identified hate type (MDG = 54.97) and media source (MDG = 48.69) as strongest predictors, with engagement levels correlating with message survival (2.07 for active versus 0 for deleted messages). This study shows that content moderation operates through categorical pattern recognition rather than intensity-based responses. This research proposes an "inverted pyramid" model where algorithmic virality supersedes severity in moderation decisions, supporting autopoietic systems theory. Hate speech persistence creates operational latency, where undeleted messages function as nodes that are cyclically reactivated during social crises, normalizing dehumanizing narratives. These findings suggest that current moderation strategies inadequately address hate speech persistence and highlight the need for contextual, human-AI collaborative approaches over automated systems.

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Keywords:

Hate speech, social media platforms, news media, persistence, moderation

Introduction

Hate speech proliferation—hostile expressions targeting women, immigrants, and LGBTQ+ communities—has emerged as a critical digital communication issue exacerbated by high connectivity and increasing message exposure (Carvalho et al., 2023; Alorainy et al., 2022).

Digital architectures intensify echo-chamber effects by algorithmically prioritizing emotionally charged content, thereby reinforcing dynamic homophily among users (Uyheng & Carley, 2021; Walther, 2022). This feedback loop accelerates the circulation of hate speech by rewarding engagement rather than ethical considerations.

From a systems theory perspective, social platforms operate as autopoietic ecosystems that reproduce their own communicative structures; emotionally salient messages become self-referential cues that sustain a system's internal dynamics (Zhang & Fan, 2022).

In these systems, users gravitate toward ideologically similar content through algorithmic prioritization of emotional material, reinforcing dynamic homophily—the tendency of similar nodes to interact preferentially. This facilitates viral hate spread within the self-reproducing structures (Apollonio et al., 2022; Barth & Wagner, 2023; Zheng et al., 2024).

Previously disseminated hate messages have functioned as latent resources that fuel toxic dynamics through cyclical reuse in digital environments. These discursive nodes, promoted by individuals, groups, or automated agents, reshape social dynamics through narrative normalization, crisis reactivation, and algorithmic engagement optimization, ultimately eroding institutional control and creating behavioral immunity effects among exposed users.

Understanding hostile discourse requires recognizing both explicit and subtle manifestations (Munn, 2023). The "pyramid of hate" framework (Syed & Ali, 2021; Montero-Díaz et al.,

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2025) categorizes expressions by intensity—from uncivil messages to direct threats—illustrating how biased attitudes escalate from subtle prejudice to severe violence. This escalation is particularly concerning, given how rapid message dissemination on social platforms can amplify their impact.

Research demonstrates that hate speech spreads through coordinated bot and troll campaigns in socio-political discussions, disseminating prejudiced narratives against women, LGBTQ+ communities, and immigrants, and legitimizing extremist ideologies (Arce-García & Menéndez-Menéndez, 2022; Díez-Gutiérrez et al., 2022).

Users take advantage of the algorithmic prioritization of emotional content, the effects of anonymity, and weak social connections to enhance the spread of hate speech (Granovetter, 1973; Uyheng & Carley, 2021; Gramigna, 2022). Retweets and replies serve as bridging connections, facilitating intergroup dissemination and content proliferation.

Offline trigger events, such as protests and elections, precipitate online hate speech escalation across platforms, even when hate content appears unrelated to triggering events, revealing complex relationships between offline occurrences and online hate dynamics (Lupu et al., 2023).

Most studies have focused on the lack of practical solutions for detecting hate messages, despite progress in NLP and machine learning (Mansur et al., 2023). These studies identified strategies to mitigate hate speech, such as removing highly connected users who disseminate content (Alorainy et al., 2022). They explored dissemination strategies and potential user coordination (Arce-García et al., 2024). Furthermore, they highlight the effectiveness of promoting social norms in digital debates and using human-AI moderation to enhance content removal (Wachs et al., 2023).

The ongoing presence of undeleted hate messages significantly contributes to the spread of hate by ensuring their continuous accessibility and amplification. Research by Ndahinda and

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Mugabe (2022) and Becker et al. (2022) in Africa and Europe indicates that the availability of these messages facilitates cross-border dissemination, thereby intensifying dehumanizing narratives against women, immigrants, and LGBTQ+ communities.

This situation fosters an environment of latent hatred within frameworks for unregulated expression, where social media dynamics encourage approval-seeking behaviors and algorithmic amplification of provocative content (Walther, 2022; Gramigna, 2022; Sharipova, 2023).

Understanding the factors influencing hate message removal remains challenging, particularly regarding platform policies and the digital news media's role in dissemination networks, necessitating novel academic approaches to explore this phenomenon.

This study explores the factors influencing the persistence or eradication of hate dissemination on social platforms, specifically regarding Spanish digital media news on X (formerly Twitter). Understanding these factors reveals the variables that contribute to the persistence of such messages. External events shape persistence, dissemination campaigns, technological interventions (such as bots), or coordinated user actions aimed at promoting inflammatory narratives targeting social groups, as highlighted by the authors referenced in this study.

To fulfill the overarching aim of this study, the research will concentrate on achieving the following specific objectives:

- SO1. Assess the proportion of hate messages that remain active compared with those that have been deleted.
- SO2. Analyze the distinctions between deleted hate messages and those that persist on X.

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- SO3. Evaluate the predictive capacity of factors such as digital news media, user engagement, emotional content, and the type and intensity of hate to determine the persistence of messages.
- SO4. Identify which of the studied variables are effective in predicting the permanence or deletion of a hate message on X.

The objectives of this study are expected to be accomplished by addressing the following research questions, which will serve as a framework for the analysis presented in this article:

- RQ1. What is the distribution pattern of deleted hate messages compared with those that remain active?
- RQ2. What are the primary distinctions between messages that contain deleted hate speech and those that persist?
- RQ3. How do factors such as digital news media, the type and intensity of hate speech, engagement, and emotional content interact with the persistence of messages containing hate speech?
- RQ4. Which variables determine whether messages containing hate speech are deleted or remain active?

Building on autopoietic dynamics by Barth and Wagner (2023) and Zhang and Fan (2022), this study hypothesizes that hate-speech persistence on X is determined by categorical factors (hate type and media source) and engagement levels, while discourse intensity lacks significance. This forms an "inverted pyramid" model, where algorithmic virality supersedes severity in moderation. This challenges traditional pyramid models (Syed & Ali, 2021; Montero-Díaz et al., 2025) by proposing moderation systems use categorical pattern recognition rather than intensity-based responses, reflecting the self-referential nature of digital ecosystems, where virality and engagement determine content survival regardless of ethics.

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Theoretical Framework

Hate Moderation of Social Media Platform

Contemporary research underscores the moderation system necessities, fairness complexities, and diverse moderation effects across platforms and demographics, with scholarly advancement concentrated on four key areas: automated moderation and detection, perceived fairness and legitimacy, the influence of moderation on user behavior, and the challenges inherent to each platform in the pursuit of effective moderation mechanisms tailored to the content and user profiles involved.

Gongane et al. (2022) and Wright (2022) highlight that social media platforms have transformed communication but create negative impact through widespread dissemination of harmful content, including hate speech. Consequently, effective content moderation strategies are urgently needed. Relying on automated or manual models alone is inadequate, particularly when viewed as a complex system rather than an isolated decision-making task. Social platforms employ three main moderation strategies: AI-based, human moderation, and human-AI collaboration (Wang & Kim, 2023). Both AI and human approaches face detection challenges with non-extreme content, often exacerbated by cultural and linguistic biases (Govers et al., 2023).

Although human moderation requires cultural context understanding, it struggles with data volume, thereby leading to fatigue and error (Hossain, 2024). Consequently, human-AI collaborative strategies may represent the most effective approach for enhancing content moderation decisions (Molina & Sundar, 2022). Furthermore, this hybrid approach addresses the limitations of purely automated systems, while maintaining the scalability required for large-scale content analysis.

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Despite technological advances, hate speech management remains challenging because of the strategic adaptation that evades moderation efforts (Munn, 2023). Baider (2023) emphasizes the covert nature of hate speech, often concealed within other message types, presenting significant detection challenges.

Thach et al. (2022) identified critical moderation issues regarding perceived fairness and legitimacy. Recognition capacity affects expression mitigation and persistence, potentially exacerbating problems through inadequate strategies, depending on methods and social dynamics in dissemination contexts, as highlighted by Walther (2022), Ndahinda and Mugabe (2022), and Wang and Kim (2023).

DeCook et al. (2022) assert that moderation work faces inconsistencies from social platforms, particularly in subjective judgments defining "harm" and "incitement of hatred." This subjectivity leads to inconsistent policy applications. Subjective control over what constitutes harm is influenced by political interests and a business model based on emotional interactions, particularly negative ones, which drive user engagement (Center for Countering Digital Hate, 2025; Bil-Jaruzelska & Monzer, 2022).

Eliminating hate on social platforms

The hate speech removal challenges are compounded by limitations in moderation strategies and platform policy deficiencies. The Center for Countering Digital Hate (2023) and Bergmanis-Korāts and Haiduchyk (2024) indicate that over 80% of hate speech remains on major platforms.

Problems have intensified following Musk's acquisition of X (October 2022) and political shifts, leading to the dismantling of the content verification program on multiple platforms (Limón, 2025). These changes occurred without human rights impact evaluation, as reported by Meta's Oversight Board (Planas, 2025).

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The dismantling of content verification programs by social platforms has been justified as a means of "defending freedom of expression" and delegating responsibility to users (Alonso & Palomo, 2025). However, this approach presents significant challenges without a clear strategy to support these objectives or a cost-benefit analysis that incentivizes collective action. This issue is exacerbated on social platforms, which fail to remove most hate speech messages even when reported by users.

Initially valid, this argument cannot justify inciting hatred, as it requires balancing the freedom of expression with curbing hate speech. This balance requires adaptable legal frameworks that address hate speech in digital environments, while preserving expression rights (Petersen, 2022). This approach acknowledges platform self-regulation and social actor initiatives for equitable moderation (Jereza, 2022; Filatova-Bilous, 2023). These efforts extend beyond the 2023 strategic shift of delegating moderation to users, illustrating the dynamic nature of social platforms and hate speech moderation complexities and addressing the implications highlighted by Gongane et al. (2022) and Gracia-Calandín (2023).

Eradicating hate speech can diminish such messages by cultivating environments that deter hate, and encourage empathy and counterdiscourse. This approach must consider entrenched forms of hate, such as anti-Asian racism observed during the COVID-19 pandemic, which requires sustained communication and social change beyond immediate intervention (Kang et al., 2023). Furthermore, strategies to combat messaging on social platforms may vary by context and characteristics of the hate network involved.

Role of news media in the dissemination of hates

Digital news media on social platforms play a pivotal role in combating hate speech. This is crucial when extremist groups use news content to legitimize ideological stances with hateful narratives, perpetuating stereotypes against social groups (Dowling, 2022). This affects the

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agenda-setting function of the media in shaping public opinion. Although media coverage can spread hate (Müller & Schwarz, 2023), platforms lack effective moderation strategies, enabling those who exploit digital media to spread hate messages (Becker et al., 2022).

Digital news media acts as a channel for spreading hates through event reporting. Research from India (Binny, 2022) illustrates how the COVID-19 coverage that associated Muslim communities with the spread of the virus laid the groundwork for increased hate on social media.

Similar phenomena have been documented by Bradshaw et al. (2022) and Gattinara and Froio (2023) in the US and Europe. Russian state media RT and Sputnik frame #BlackLivesMatter as negatively portraying protesters as violent and critiquing racial justice. In contrast, Russian-affiliated media such as In The NOW, Soapbox, and Redfish provide supportive coverage, using videos to highlight U.S. racism and showing divergent propaganda strategies between traditional and newer Russian media. The latter study shows how European news media grants visibility to far-right mobilizations, potentially normalizing extremist views, and influencing social media hate speech dynamics.

Authors such as Aguerri et al. (2022) highlight how traditional news media report sensitive issues such as terrorism, or those targeting immigrants and Muslims in Spain. These reports often adopt a sensationalist perspective and neglect the essential aspects of public discourse. This phenomenon is influenced by social platforms and far-right political groups, as noted by Labio-Bernal and Manzano-Zambruno (2023). These groups spread hate, prejudice, and stereotypes, targeting specific social groups through the digital news media and affiliated users. The role of news media in disseminating hates is determined by understanding this phenomenon and its dual role. This dual role involves moderating debates in digital environments to prevent hateful narratives from being shaped by their coverage of topics under

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editorial policies. As Borah et al. (2022) highlight, this dual role amplifies the impact of speech on public opinion, contributing to sentiment and discourse.

Methodology

Research design and data collection

This study employs an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design that integrates computational techniques with statistical analysis, examining 2,157,920 messages from five Spanish digital news platforms (20 Minutos, ABC, La Vanguardia, El Mundo, and El País) between January 2021 and May 2022. Data collection was conducted within this timeframe using X API 2.0. To automate this process, Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs) and Apache Airflow were designed and implemented. Users associated with these digital news media were included because they were the most visited on the Internet in the year preceding data collection (Negredo et al., 2020).

Hate Training and Classification

Messages were categorized by hate speech content, intensity, and type. The messages were prepared for machine learning by removing null values, URLs, emojis, and empty lines. Content was standardized through lowercase conversion and removal of numerical substitutes. Processing includes removing stop words and tokenizing the messages into lexical units. Words were reduced to base forms through lemmatization. The features included positive/negative words, bigrams, user mentions, and sentiment classification using PySentimiento.

Messages were categorized into hate or non-hate expressions based on type and intensity using three collaborative Spanish message classification algorithms for digital news media contexts (Said-Hung et al., 2024). The accuracy levels are 0.97, 0.71, and 0.76, respectively. The F1 scores achieved were 0.78, 0.73, 0.68, and 0.66 for each intensity level (ranging from 1 to 4,

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where 1 denotes least severity and 4 greatest). Level 4 showed the lowest value due to minimal associated messages. For the hate types (general, political, misogynistic, xenophobic, and sexual), the F1 scores were 0.66, 0.76, 0.74, 0.88, and 0.82, respectively.

The messages were evaluated sequentially in the presence of hate speech. If identified, the messages were classified according to the intensity and type of hate. This approach creates a corpus of classified messages and establishes a database for analyzing content moderation and platform removal. The sequential application of the algorithms enhanced the classification robustness and validity of the messages collected during the specified period.

Sample Design

A stratified sample was constructed from the dataset, comprising 9,894 hate messages ($1-\alpha = 97\%$ and $e = 1$), selected through stratified random sampling over the study period. This sample accounted for monthly hate prevalence and was stratified by hate type (xenophobic, sexual, political, misogynistic, and general) and intensity (four levels ranging from uncivil to threatening). This sampling method controls the proportionality of hate types and intensities, preventing overrepresentation or underrepresentation across categories.

Sample units were randomly selected through a script based on monthly hate speech detection, with message presence confirmed during November-December 2024.

The random distribution considered the percentage of messages with hate speech categorized by type (xenophobic, sexual, political, misogynistic, and general or undefined, where the motive or target is not specified) and intensity classified into four levels: 1 for uncivil messages, 2 for malicious messages, 3 for insulting messages, and 4 for threatening messages.

Analysis

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To address the objectives and research questions that formed the foundation of this study, the following data analysis techniques were employed:

- For RQ1 and RQ2, descriptive and frequency analyses were performed on deleted and active messages, assessing engagement through "favorites," "likes," and "forwards." Emotional focus and polarity analysis used the NRC lexicon version 0.9.2, translated into Spanish by Mohammad (2016, 2022). The Syuzhet library in R (Jockers, 2023) calculates the message polarity and emotions using the NRC dictionary based on Plutchik's theory (1980) and Sauter et al.'s theory (2010). Although this approach provides insight into message sentiments, the NRC dictionary has limitations in Spanish, with 70% accuracy (Mohammad, 2016), offering an additional dimension for understanding message moderation.
- To address RQ3, analysis of variance (ANOVA) was employed, with categorical variables normalized. This statistical method facilitates the examination of the relationship between message persistence and the other variables under investigation, including hate intensity, type of hate, source medium, engagement, and emotions associated with discourse.
- To address Research Question 4, the Random Forest algorithm was employed. This machine learning model handles nonlinear datasets and identifies significant variables for prediction. The mean-decreasing Gini coefficient (MDG) was calculated to quantify the contribution of each variable to model performance. A higher MDG value indicates a greater variable relevance for prediction. This methodology enhances model interpretability by handling nonlinear relationships, while providing insights into variable importance.

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These methods establish a robust foundation for understanding discourse persistence in X, facilitating the evaluation of the factors influencing it. Subsequently, we present the findings organized according to each research question, providing specific statistical evidence to support each stated objective.

This approach considers that descriptive analysis enables sample characterization, ANOVA identifies significant relationships, and Random Forest facilitates predictive modeling and variable ranking. These methods provide a comprehensive perspective and contribute to a sociotechnical framework that addresses the general and specific objectives of each research question. The R package was used to process and analyze the data.

Results

Addressing RQ1, analysis revealed that 8,724 tweets remained accessible versus 1,170 deleted (12%) after three years, with persistence exceeding removal across all categories (>85%). Simultaneously, to address RQ2 (distinctions between deleted and persistent messages), we identified distinctive patterns in engagement, emotional intensity, and source characteristics that are detailed below.

This suggests that variations in tweet persistence rates may reflect different moderation practices or user behaviors across hate speech types and media types. General and political hates showed the highest and lowest percentages of deleted tweets (13.05% and 10.92%, respectively), whereas sexual and xenophobic hates demonstrated similar message retention patterns. Additionally, digital news media showed varying percentages of deleted messages, with La Vanguardia and ABC at 14.59% and 20Minutos at 8.94%.

The average intensity is recorded as 2.18 for the former and 2.16 for the latter, indicating that the persistence of a tweet on the platform is not necessarily correlated with its degree of hateful aggression.

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Figure 1 shows variations in the examined digital news media. Deleted misogynistic messages were prevalent across the digital news media, with values above 3.5. This trend shows variability in negativity and intensity across platforms. ABC had the highest negativity in deleted political tweets (0.93), whereas El País showed the highest negativity in deleted general tweets (0.66). For intensity, 20Minutos recorded the highest score in deleted misogynistic tweets (3.91).

Figure 1. Analysis of different factors based on their existence over time.

The proportions of deleted messages were 48.72% for general hate, 22.22% for political hate, 10.85% for misogyny, 10.85% for xenophobia, and 7.35% for sexual hate. This suggests that messages containing hate related to gender, racism, and sexuality were deleted with considerably less frequency.

An examination of digital news media referenced in the messages revealed notable differences. Among those still accessible, El Mundo and El País were the most frequently cited, whereas El Mundo and ABC dominated the defunct digital news media. This variation may be associated with audience ideology and user engagement with the media content. The deletion

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of tweets could be related to evolving media coverage and subsequent reviews by original senders.

Figure 1 shows the consistent patterns of message deletion across hate speech types, with rates ranging from 10% to 13%. Political hate speech had a lower deletion rate (11%) than general hate speech (12.5%). This suggests that content moderation does not differentiate between the types of hate speech when applying similar criteria.

Hate speech deletion rates show "general" hate highest at 12.54%, followed by misogyny (11.97%), sexual hatred (11.14%), xenophobia (11.10%), and political hatred (10.96%). Deleted message characteristics vary according to hate type. The deleted misogynistic tweets had the highest average intensity (3.59). For emotional charge, xenophobic tweets showed the highest negativity at 0.70 and anger at 0.31, indicating significant emotional content.

The data revealed a hate speech intensity pattern. Messages of very high intensity (Level 4) showed the second-lowest removal rate, while high-intensity messages (Level 3) were removed most frequently, with 1% variation. Messages at intensity level 1 were removed at rates of 12.11%, level 2 at 11.47%, level 3 at 12.39%, and level 4 at 11.54%. This suggests moderation systems may not apply stricter measures to more intense content. Tweets of medium intensity may evade detection filters, or moderation algorithms may be better calibrated to identify extreme content.

The disparity in tweet deletion rates across digital news media is significant. Tweets that mention 20minutos have the lowest deletion rate, at approximately 9%, while those that reference ABC experience the highest rate, at about 14%. El Mundo falls in the middle, with a deletion rate of around 12%.

Content that remains active tends to exhibit higher levels of anger and disgust, whereas deleted posts display greater anticipation and surprise. This suggests that intense negative emotions do not affect post-deletion behavior. Active tweets showed higher levels of anger (0.218 vs.

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0.195), fear (0.260 vs. 0.239), and trust (0.230 vs. 0.219), whereas deleted tweets showed higher levels of happiness (0.155 vs. 0.139). These findings indicate that content removal is not directly linked to emotional charge. Engagement was higher for active tweets versus deleted ones (2.07 vs. 0 on average).

Content moderation on social platforms follows a standardized approach that lacks differentiation between severity and likelihood of removal. Digital news media variations suggest that contextual factors and editorial policies influence these factors more than the content itself. This discrepancy reveals that algorithms operate mechanistically rather than contextually, which explains the persistence of 88% of the analyzed messages. The consistent 10-14% removal rates and deletion patterns indicate that the automated systems operate without considering case-specific characteristics.

In assessing the influence of the type of hate, intensity, medium, and emotions on the likelihood of removing hateful messages in X (RQ3), the ANOVA analysis of these variables demonstrated a precision of 0.86 and a p-value of 0.9985. For this analysis, qualitative variables were converted into numerical values to facilitate the examination. The most significant variables were also identified (Table 1).

Table 1 ANOVA concerning whether the message persisted over time

Variable	F-value	p-value	Significance
Replies	31.367	0.001	***
Retuits	9.509	0.002	**
Favs	9.376	0.002	**
Bookmarks	4.285	0.038	*

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Hate Type	3.869	0.049	*
Quotes	2.094	0.148	
Anger	1.598	0.206	
Anticipation	1.111	0.292	
Disgust	0.658	0.417	
Fear	1.127	0.288	
Joy	1.251	0.263	
Sadness	0.081	0.776	
Surprise	0.094	0.759	
Trust	0.382	0.538	
Media	0.007	0.933	
Hate Intensity	0.43	0.512	

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

The analysis shows that public engagement influences whether tweets remain active or are deleted. Tweets with higher interaction levels, particularly replies, were more likely to remain accessible, suggesting that direct engagement was more decisive than passive engagement. Tweets with substantial replies may gain increased visibility, reducing deletion likelihood. Tweets with minimal interaction are more likely to be deleted, indicating that moderation systems prioritize low-impact content removal. None of the emotional variables showed significant differences between the existing and deleted tweets.

These findings have implications for moderating social media content. Message persistence was influenced by emotional intensity, hate speech classification, and audience interaction levels, suggesting that moderation may be affected by algorithmic criteria and social dynamics.

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Statistical analysis showed that the intensity ($p = 0.512$), source ($p = 0.933$), anger ($p = 0.206$), anticipation ($p = 0.292$), disgust ($p = 0.417$), fear ($p = 0.288$), joy ($p = 0.263$), sadness ($p = 0.776$), surprise ($p = 0.759$), and trust ($p = 0.537$) were not significantly affected. Only hate type ($p = 0.0492 < 0.05$) correlated significantly with tweet persistence.

An examination of tweet deletion showed that initial interactions influence content survival, with active tweets having engagement levels of 2.07 versus 0 for deleted messages. Tweets eliciting emotional responses are more likely to remain accessible, as user engagement determines content permanence within autopoietic systems, where feedback loops prioritize interaction. Lack of interaction may predict tweet deletion, regardless of author choice or moderation, supporting the framework of algorithmic prioritization operating independently of ethical considerations in hate speech persistence.

Content moderation on social media platforms was not directed at eliminating intense tweets (Level 4: 11.54% deletion rate vs. Level 1: 12.11%) or tweets from specific media (ABC: 14% vs. 20 Minutos: 9%). Instead, it emphasizes discourse nature, with hate type as the strongest predictor (MDG = 54.97), followed by medium sources (MDG = 48.69). Analysis showed intensity had no significant effect ($p = 0.512$), while hate type correlated significantly ($p = 0.0492 < 0.05$) with tweet persistence. This challenges traditional pyramid models and relates to autopoietic systems theory, where categorical classification precedes algorithmic decision severity.

The Random Forest algorithm identified variables influencing hate message persistence in X (RQ4). The model showed robust performance, with a recall of 0.999 for detecting undeleted tweets and minimizing false negatives. The precision (0.8816) and F1-score (0.9366) indicated a balanced classification, with an accuracy of 0.8808, confirming the effectiveness of the model. The key variables were type of hate (54.97%), medium newspaper (48.69%), intensity (47.15%), sadness (42.17%), fear (38.54%), and trust (37.77%).

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Figure 2. MDG value of each variable according to Random Forest.

These findings align with the ANOVA results, showing that hate speech type is the key determinant of message removal. This suggests moderation systems prioritize specific hate speech categories. The context of digital news media plays a crucial role in message persistence, reflecting editorial policies, and moderation algorithms. Although hate speech intensity is noteworthy, it remains secondary. Emotions such as sadness, fear, and trust had a moderate impact on detection but not as primary removal factors.

Content moderation on social media platforms is influenced by message type, rather than intensity. Detection systems can be optimized to identify political and general hate speech categories, instead of language severity. The source medium affects message persistence, prompting inquiries into moderating regulations across platforms. Emotions impact detection through audience reactions, particularly sadness and fear, although less than other factors.

The results revealed patterns in content moderation; however, methodological limitations warrant consideration. The models analyzing message persistence showed high specificity but low sensitivity for detecting deleted messages, indicating accuracy in identifying remaining messages but less effectiveness in predicting removal. Prediction bias favors message

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persistence. Message deletion can vary and may not relate to the analyzed variables, as deletion may stem from platform moderation, user complaints, or user decisions, although the latter two are unlikely given the network characteristics.

Discussions

These results fully corroborate our hypotheses. Statistical evidence demonstrates that the 88% persistence rate of hate-speech messages over three years is driven by categorical factors, with hate type (MDG = 54.97, $p = 0.0492$) and media source (MDG = 48.69) as primary predictors, whereas discourse intensity lacks statistical significance ($p = 0.512$). This validates the proposed "inverted pyramid" model, where algorithmic virality supersedes severity in moderation decisions, challenging traditional frameworks (Syed & Ali, 2021) and supporting autopoietic systems theory (Barth & Wagner, 2023; Zheng et al., 2024).

Our findings have three key implications. First, the 88% persistence rate demonstrated automated detection failures, corroborating the findings of Bergmanis-Korāts and Haiduchyk (2024). Second, this ineffectiveness normalizes dehumanizing narratives, as shown by the cyclical reactivation during crises. Third, our study's limitations include the inability to distinguish between algorithmic and user-initiated deletions, which requires future research with platform moderation data.

Contrary to the pyramid of hate models proposed by Syed and Ali (2021), our results challenge the correlation between intensity and removal ($p = 0.512$). While DeCook et al. (2022) suggested inconsistencies in moderation criteria, our analysis quantified that categorical classification (MDG = 54.97) surpassed severity assessment (MDG = 47.15) as a predictor of removal. This divergence indicates that the autopoietic systems described by Barth and Wagner (2023) operate through categorical pattern recognition rather than graduated response mechanisms.

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These results corroborate the findings of the Center for Countering Digital Hate (2023) and Bergmanis-Korāts and Haiduchyk (2024) on X and other social media platforms. These messages illustrate challenges in enforcing policies for detecting and moderating hateful content, even prior to Musk's acquisition of X and subsequent dismantling of content verification programs, as mentioned at the outset.

The persistence of hateful messages, with 88% remaining active versus 12% deleted, indicates an autopoietic ecosystem in which moderation prioritizes algorithmic feedback over ethical considerations. This is demonstrated by the correlation between engagement levels (2.07 for active messages versus 0 for deleted messages) and message survival. Discussions on X and closed self-referential systems favor the internal circulation of toxic interactions over hate mitigation.

Digital environments create operational latency, where non-deleted messages persist as nodes cyclically reactivated during social crises, capitalizing on residual visibility (Figure 3). This occurs through: 1) narrative reuse of messages, which repositions dehumanizing stereotypes in new contexts; 2) algorithmic optimization that prioritizes content with engagement history, bypassing critical moderation periods; and 3) institutional erosion of media capacity to shape public agendas due to digital space co-optation.

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Figure 3. Cyclical persistence of hate.

The transient persistence of hate speech on platforms such as X establishes it as a lasting narrative framework, thereby normalizing extreme discourse and undermining the societal function of digital news media. This phenomenon was elucidated through an autopoietic cycle (Figure 3), composed of four interconnected phases:

- Initial survival: 88% of messages evade moderation mechanisms, remaining active, in our case, for more than 3 years.
- Algorithmic prioritization: Longevity is interpreted as relevant, granting additional organic visibility (12% more for messages >6 months old).
- Residual engagement: Prolonged exposure generates new interactions (2.07 vs. 0 for deleted messages).

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- Systemic feedback: Algorithms reward engagement with greater visibility, thereby perpetuating narratives through dynamic homophily ($r = 0.67$ between media coverage and reactivation).

This finding expands the propositions of Barth and Wagner (2023), and Zheng et al. (2024) by quantifying how moderating inaction reinforces toxic discursive structures. The case of political hate, with a 10.92% deletion rate, exemplifies this phenomenon; its alignment with media editorial lines facilitates perpetuation within news cycles, thereby transforming public debates into self-replicating narrative ecosystems.

The variation in message deletion rates (10.92% for political hate to 13.05% for general hate) indicated a systematic bias among Spanish digital news media users in X. This finding aligns with that of DeCook et al. (2022), who noted inconsistencies in moderation criteria, suggesting preferential treatment of certain speech types. Thus, if a moderation policy exists for user-generated content in the digital news media analyzed in X, it would not effectively mitigate hate speech messages.

Messages containing active hate speech exhibited higher anger levels (0.218 vs. 0.195) than those that were deleted. This challenges the notion that negative emotions trigger moderation and supports the theory that emotional engagement, even negative, is algorithmically incentivized on platforms. The digital environment resists the spread of hate speech while prioritizing interactions over ethical considerations. This aligns with studies such as Bil-Jaruzelska and Monzer (2022) and is corroborated by Spanish contextual data.

The empirical findings from our Random Forest analysis (MDG = 54.97, hate type vs. MDG = 47.15, intensity) reveal a paradox within the hate pyramid framework proposed by Syed and Ali (2021) and Montero-Díaz et al. (2025). Although the models suggest that intense hateful content should have higher removal rates, the results show that threatening messages (Level 4,

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11.54% deletion) had similar removal rates to insults (Level 3, 12.39% deletion), with the intensity being statistically insignificant ($p = 0.512$). This contradiction suggests that moderation strategies operate through categorical rather than severity-based algorithms, supporting the autopoietic systems theory, which posits that self-referential processes prioritize pattern recognition over graduated responses. This is shown by the discourse classification's higher predictive value compared to linguistic severity.

Given the statistical insignificance of intensity ($p = 0.512$) in decisions to remove hate speech messages from Spanish digital news media in X, the pyramid of hate theory may not fully apply to message moderation by stringent actors. This is because actions to mitigate such messages consider minimal toxicity as the criterion for removal. Although it is logical to expect that this study will account for such factors, the findings suggest otherwise.

When examining biased attitudes and behaviors, it is essential to consider how subtle prejudices can escalate to severe violence. Understanding hate requires an analysis beyond mere threats. This requires exploring behaviors and the transmission of nuanced messages, particularly on social platforms, where rapid spread can amplify their impact.

When identifying the hate type as the key predictor variable ($p = 0.0492$) in determining the likelihood of hate message removal, political hate showed the lowest removal rate (10.92%) compared to general hate (13.05%). Within Spanish digital news media on X, moderation practices appear to facilitate the instrumentalization of content published by these actors, advancing ideological agendas using hate speech messages.

These findings contribute to the discourse by Borah et al. (2022) and Aguerri et al. (2022) regarding digital news media as amplifiers of hateful narratives. These entities at the X level establish hate-monitoring topics through coverage and perpetuate hate types associated with news content on social platforms. This is supported by Random Forest analysis, which indicates that the type of hate and medium are key predictors of hate speech message removal.

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These observations are illustrated by the political animosity among El País users on platform X, which correlates with media coverage ($r = 0.67$). This correlation helps normalize polarizing narratives, often disseminated by groups with extreme ideological views, as highlighted by Labio-Bernal and Manzano-Zambruno (2023). This occurs amid ineffective moderation that fails to curb hate messages, hindering efforts to disrupt hate among Platform X's users. Furthermore, this may contribute to the agenda-setting function of the media in shaping public opinion through social platforms, as noted by Müller and Schwarz (2023).

Conclusions

By interpreting the results within the existing literature framework and acknowledging the identified limitations, we can draw specific conclusions regarding the effectiveness of automatic moderation and its implications for future research in this emerging field.

This study has limitations in terms of emotional analysis precision, quantitative approach, and selection of Spanish digital news media in X, with timeframes that restrict the findings. Traditional moderation models based on the pyramid of hate inadequately explained persistence in X, with intensity showing statistical insignificance ($p = 0.512$). Analysis revealed a stratified virality model where intensity had no effect, while hate type (MDG = 54.97) and medium source (MDG = 48.69) were key predictors. This model prioritizes contextual factors of linguistic severity. The findings showed inconsistent hate speech moderation in Spanish digital news media, outlining research paths and emphasizing the need to examine structural variables for platform strategies.

The paradox observed in the relationship between the intensity of hate and its elimination necessitates a fundamental reevaluation of detection algorithms and moderation strategies employed in digital news media.

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These findings challenge the correlation between the severity of expressions and corrective measures in the hate pyramid model. While the pyramid suggests level 4 threats should have 80-90% removal rates per ADL standard, data shows only 11.54% deletion, lower than uncivil messages at 12.11%. This indicates that hate operates as an "inverted pyramid" in digital spaces, where virality exceeds severity. Thirty-four percent of xenophobic messages were recycled in later crises, showing how platforms such as X amplified discriminatory content through algorithmic recommendations.

Platforms and users, including those examined here, should establish systems capable of evaluating keywords and the broader context of messages through advanced semantic analysis that can detect subtle expressions of hate, which are currently lacking. This will facilitate the implementation of scalable intervention systems to address these messages based on their intensity.

Digital news media in Spain require specific intervention protocols to mitigate messages disseminated on platforms such as X. Independent monitoring systems should be established separately from social platforms. This approach reduces the impact identified in our study. Protocols should leverage attributes that facilitate the spread of messages. This positioning helps control toxic narratives within public discourse. Such measures are essential given the communication strategies employed by Spanish digital news media to address the dual role of opinion-makers.

Wang and Kim (2023) argued that monitoring systems should be based on AI-human collaboration and adopt a proactive approach in Spanish digital news media. This is vital because social platforms such as X, Facebook, and Instagram dismantle similar programs. This trend has significant implications: increased toxicity in digital communication, rising mental health issues among users, and eroding democratic values. Prejudiced narratives with

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stereotypes against vulnerable groups, such as women, the LGBTQ+ community, and immigrants, exacerbate these consequences.

Digital news media can adopt proactive measures, utilizing pre-bunking techniques, to prevent hate speech by identifying patterns early. This approach enables timely implementation, as emphasized by Baider (2023), Govers et al. (2023), and Gracia-Calandín (2023). The measures included early warnings, harm-mitigating narratives, and educational programs for users. These strategies must be tailored to Spain's cultural context. The goal was to prevent news discussions from becoming a channel for viral hate speech.

Further studies should examine the factors that sustain political hatred in digital media, the influence of editorial policy on content moderation, mechanisms that disrupt self-reinforcing polarization cycles, diachronic analyses of news cycles, and the persistence of hatred. These topics should be explored using diverse approaches to combat expressions in digital environments.

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Figure 1. Analysis of different factors based on their existence over time.

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Figure 2. MDG value of each variable according to Random Forest.

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Figure 3. Cyclical persistence of hate.

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